

Clinical models and predictors of retained products of conception following induced abortion: a systematic review and meta-analysis

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REVIEW TITLE AND BASIC DETAILS

Review title

Clinical models and predictors of retained products of conception following induced abortion: a systematic review and meta-analysis

Condition or domain being studied

This review focuses on the identification and diagnostic accuracy of clinical predictors, ultrasound findings, and biochemical markers associated with retained products of conception (RPOC) in women who have undergone induced abortion. The aim is to synthesize existing evidence on models or variables that could help guide postabortion clinical decision-making and reduce unnecessary surgical interventions.

Rationale for the review

Although the safety and effectiveness of induced abortion are well established, the diagnosis of retained products of conception (RPOC) remains inconsistent and often subjective. Currently, there is no comprehensive synthesis of clinical, ultrasound, and biochemical predictors to guide the early identification of RPOC. This review aims to fill this gap by systematically evaluating predictive models and diagnostic variables to support evidence-based decision-making, reduce unnecessary surgical interventions, and improve postabortion care outcomes.

Review objectives

To evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of clinical models and individual predictors—including symptoms, ultrasound findings, and biochemical markers—for detecting retained products of conception (RPOC) in women following induced abortion. The review will also explore which combinations of predictors offer the highest sensitivity and specificity, and assess their potential utility in clinical decision-making.

Keywords

Retained products of conception; Induced abortion; Clinical prediction models; Diagnostic accuracy; ultrasound in abortion care; biochemical markers after abortion; Endometrial thickness; postabortion complications; uterine evacuation; postabortion management; beta-hCG monitoring

Country

Mexico

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Population

Included

Women of reproductive age who have undergone a medical or surgical induced abortion, regardless of gestational age, in any healthcare setting (hospital, outpatient, or community-based).

Excluded

Women with spontaneous abortion (miscarriage), childbirth, ectopic pregnancy, or molar pregnancy; studies involving mixed populations without stratified data for induced abortion will also be excluded.

Intervention(s) or exposure(s)

Included

The review will include studies that assess any clinical, imaging, or biochemical indicator used to predict or diagnose retained products of conception (RPOC) after induced abortion. Eligible exposures include individual symptoms (e.g. pain, bleeding, fever), ultrasound findings (e.g. endometrial thickness, presence of intrauterine material), and biochemical markers (e.g. beta-hCG decline, pregnancy test result). Studies evaluating combined predictive models or decision-support tools will also be included.

Excluded

Studies will be excluded if they assess interventions not intended for the diagnosis or prediction of retained products of conception (RPOC), such as therapeutic treatments (e.g. antibiotics, surgical procedures) without diagnostic intent. Studies focusing solely on predictors of complications unrelated to RPOC (e.g. infection, hemorrhage) or involving exposures during spontaneous abortion, childbirth, or ectopic pregnancy will also be excluded.

Comparator(s) or control(s)

Included

Comparators will include any reference standard used to confirm the presence or absence of retained products of conception (RPOC) following induced abortion. These may include surgical intervention (e.g. reaspiration), clinical diagnosis by follow-up resolution without further intervention (watchful waiting), negative pregnancy test results, or follow-up ultrasound findings confirming uterine evacuation. Studies that compare predictor performance against any of these outcomes will be included.

Excluded

Studies will be excluded if they use a comparator unrelated to the diagnosis of retained products of conception (RPOC), such as treatment outcomes not linked to diagnostic confirmation. Comparators based on non-clinical judgment without follow-up or lacking any reference standard for confirming RPOC will also be excluded.

Study design

Both randomized and nonrandomized study types will be included.

Included

This review will include diagnostic accuracy studies of any design, including prospective and retrospective cohort studies, case-control studies, and randomized controlled trials, provided they evaluate the ability of clinical, ultrasound, or biochemical predictors to detect retained products of conception (RPOC) following induced abortion. Studies must report or allow calculation of sensitivity, specificity, or other diagnostic accuracy metrics.

Excluded

Studies will be excluded if they do not assess diagnostic accuracy, do not report relevant outcomes (e.g. sensitivity, specificity), or do not use a reference standard to confirm the presence or absence of retained products of conception (RPOC). Editorials, narrative reviews, letters, commentaries, case reports, and studies focusing solely on spontaneous abortion, childbirth, or ectopic/molar pregnancies will also be excluded.

Context

This review will include studies conducted in any healthcare setting, including hospitals, outpatient clinics, community-based services, or telemedicine environments, provided they evaluate women after an induced abortion. There will be no geographic restrictions; studies from both high-income and low- and middle-income countries will be considered. The focus is on postabortion diagnostic practices, regardless of whether care was provided by specialists or general providers.

TIMELINE OF THE REVIEW

Date of first submission to PROSPERO

26 June 2025

Review timeline

Start date: 25 June 2025. End date: 15 December 2025.

Date of registration in PROSPERO

26 June 2025

AVAILABILITY OF FULL PROTOCOL

Availability of full protocol

A full protocol has been written and uploaded to PROSPERO. The protocol may be accessed through this link

<https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/PROSPEROFILES/bed99521907618bf88ee56c4cd1de718.pdf>.

SEARCHING AND SCREENING

Search for unpublished studies

Only unpublished studies will be sought.

Main bibliographic databases that will be searched

The main databases to be searched are *CENTRAL - Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials*, *CINAHL - Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature*, *Embase - Embase via Ovid*, *LILACS - Latin American and Caribbean Health Sciences Literature*, *MEDLINE*, *PubMed* and *Scopus*.

Other important or specialist databases that will be searched

ClinicalTrials.gov, WHO International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP), OpenGrey, Google Scholar, ProQuest Dissertations and Theses, and institutional repositories related to reproductive health and abortion care.

Search language restrictions

There are no language restrictions.

Search date restrictions

Databases will be searched for articles published from 1 January 2000, there are no search end date restrictions.

Other methods of identifying studies

Other studies will be identified by: *contacting authors or experts, looking through all the articles that cite the papers included in the review ("snowballing"), reference list checking, searching conference proceedings, searching dissertation and thesis databases and searching trial or study registers.*

Additional information about identifying studies

In addition to database searching, we will identify studies by manually checking the reference lists of included articles, searching clinical trial registries (e.g., ClinicalTrials.gov, WHO ICTRP), reviewing conference proceedings, screening dissertations and theses, contacting subject-matter experts, and using citation tracking ("snowballing") to identify relevant literature not captured.

Link to search strategy

A full search strategy is available in the full protocol as described in the *Availability of full protocol* section

Selection process

Studies will be screened independently by at least two people (or person/machine combination) with a process to resolve differences.

Other relevant information about searching and screening

Titles and abstracts will be screened independently by two reviewers. Full-text articles will be retrieved for all studies deemed potentially relevant. Discrepancies at either stage will be resolved through discussion or consultation with a third party if needed. We will use Rayyan and/or manual screening tools to assist in the selection process. Records of reasons for exclusion at the full-text stage will be maintained for the PRISMA flow diagram.

DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

Data extraction from published articles and reports

Data will be extracted independently by at least two people (or person/machine combination) with a process to resolve differences.

Authors will be asked to provide any required data not available in published reports.

Study risk of bias or quality assessment

Risk of bias will be assessed using: *QUADAS-2*

Data will be assessed independently by at least two people (or person/machine combination) with a process to resolve differences.

Additional information will be sought from study investigators if required information is unclear or unavailable in the study publications/reports.

Reporting bias assessment

Risk of bias due to missing results will be assessed using funnel plots (if ≥ 10 studies), Egger's test for small-study effects, and comparison of protocols with reported outcomes. Suspected selective reporting will prompt author contact. Findings will inform the overall assessment of evidence quality.

Certainty assessment

We will use the GRADE approach to assess the certainty of evidence for key outcomes, considering study limitations, inconsistency, indirectness, imprecision, and publication bias. The assessment will be conducted independently by two reviewers, and disagreements will be resolved through discussion. Summary of Findings tables will be developed accordingly.

OUTCOMES TO BE ANALYSED

Main outcomes

Primary outcome: Diagnostic accuracy of clinical and imaging criteria for identifying retained products of conception (RPC) following induced abortion.

Definition: Presence of RPC confirmed by histopathology, reintervention, or sustained positive hCG levels.

Measurements: Sensitivity, specificity, positive/negative predictive value, likelihood ratios (LR+/LR-), and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC-ROC).

Time point: Within 30 days post-abortion.

Effect measures: Sensitivity, specificity, LR+/LR-, AUC.

Additional outcomes

1. Clinical symptoms associated with retained products of conception (RPC)

Definition: Symptoms such as abnormal bleeding, pelvic pain, fever, or foul-smelling discharge.

Measurement: Proportion of patients presenting each symptom; odds ratios (OR) where available.

Time point: Within 30 days post-abortion.

Effect measure: Frequency, OR.

2. Association between ultrasound findings and need for reintervention

Definition: Correlation between sonographic parameters (e.g., endometrial thickness, Doppler flow) and subsequent surgical or medical reintervention.

Measurement: Sensitivity, specificity, relative risk (RR).

Time point: Within 30 days.

Effect measure: RR, sensitivity, specificity.

3. Impact of initial abortion method on RPC detection

Definition: Comparison of RPC rates and detection accuracy following medical vs surgical abortion.

Measurement: RPC incidence, diagnostic accuracy by method.

Effect measure: Risk difference, OR.

PLANNED DATA SYNTHESIS

Strategy for data synthesis

Diagnostic accuracy measures (sensitivity, specificity, LR+, LR-, AUC) will be pooled using a bivariate random-effects model or hierarchical summary receiver operating characteristic (HSROC) model, depending on the availability and heterogeneity of data. Meta-analyses will be conducted using RevMan and/or R (meta and mada packages).

CURRENT REVIEW STAGE

Stage of the review at this submission

Review stage	Started	Completed
Pilot work	✓	
Formal searching/study identification		

Review stage**Started****Completed**

Screening search results against inclusion criteria

Data extraction or receipt of IPD

Risk of bias/quality assessment

Data synthesis

Review status

The review is currently planned or ongoing.

Publication of review results

Results of the review will be published in English and Spanish.

REVIEW AFFILIATION, FUNDING AND PEER REVIEW

Review team members

Dr Mauricio Rangel (review guarantor and contact) ORCID: 0000-0002-7842-5207. Medica Center Fem. Mexico.

No conflict of interest declared.

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No conflict of interest declared.

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Funding source

Review has no funding and no agreed support from an academic institution and is done in authors' own time.

Additional information about funding

This review has no specific funding. It is conducted independently by the principal investigator as part of academic development, without financial support from any institution, organization, or sponsor.

Peer review

The protocol was peer reviewed and approved by the Research Ethics Committee of Medica Center Fem, which is registered with COFEPRIS (Federal Commission for the Protection Against Health Risks) in Mexico. The committee evaluated the scientific and ethical integrity of the review design.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Additional information

This systematic review is part of an independent academic initiative to improve diagnostic and management strategies for suspected retained products of conception after induced abortion. It aims to address a current gap in the literature by synthesizing available clinical, imaging, and follow-up data relevant to low- and middle-income countries, particularly in Latin America.

Review conflict of interest

Declared individual interests are recorded under team member details.. No additional interests are recorded for this review.

Medical Subject Headings

Abortion, Induced; Abortion, Legal; Placenta, Retained; Diagnostic Imaging; Ultrasonography; Uterine Hemorrhage; Dilatation and Curettage; Curettage; Misoprostol; Mifepristone; Aftercare; Uterine Diseases; Sensitivity and Specificity; Risk Assessment; Observer Variation; Follow-Up Studies; Endometrium

SIMILAR REVIEWS

Check for similar records already in PROSPERO

PROSPERO identified a number of existing PROSPERO records that were similar to this one (last check made on 25 June 2025). These are shown below along with the reasons given by that the review team for the reviews being different and/or proceeding.

- Systematic review of diagnostic strategies and clinical outcomes in infiltrative vascular retained products of conception (IVRPC) and their relationship to pregnancy-related uterine arteriovenous malformations (AVMs) [published 1 June 2025] [CRD420251063938]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- The accuracy of ultrasound scan in predicting retained products of conception following a pregnancy- includes termination, miscarriage and delivery. [published 25 July 2021] [CRD42021254687]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Artificial Intelligence-Driven Prediction of Free Flap Failure in Microsurgery A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis [published 6 May 2025] [CRD420251047313]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Clinical Utility of Large Language Models in Lung Cancer Patients: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis Protocol [published 29 May 2025] [CRD420251063404]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Influence of retained products of conception on fertility: a systematic review [published 25 July 2016] [CRD42016042444]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Association between premature mortality with spontaneous and induced abortion: A systematic review and meta-analysis [published 3 October 2024] [CRD42024594169]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Meta-analysis of the clinical value of different types of biomarkers in the diagnosis of silicosis [published 4 May 2024] [CRD42024539419]. The review was judged **not to be similar**

- Use of imaging tests in the diagnostic management of breast pain: a systematic review [published 18 May 2025] [CRD420251055147]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Clinical Prediction Models for Sudden Cardiac Death After Myocardial Infarction: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis [published 2 August 2024] [CRD42024572352]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Complications of second-trimester medical and surgical abortion [published 8 September 2023] [CRD42023458724]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Diagnostic Workup for Pseudarthrosis Following Spinal Fusion: A Systematic Review [published 14 January 2025] [CRD42025611609]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Artificial Intelligence-Based Diagnostic Models for Tongue Cancer: A Systematic Review [published 20 May 2025] [CRD420251057390]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Diagnostic accuracy of clinical tests in diagnosing acute diverticulitis, a systematic review and meta-analysis. [published 10 February 2021] [CRD42021230622]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Diagnostic Models for Sepsis-Associated Encephalopathy: A Comprehensive Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis [published 27 May 2025] [CRD420251062747]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Application of Machine Learning in diagnosis of cardiomyopathies from clinical imaging modalities. A systematic review, diagnostic accuracy meta-analysis, meta-regression and evaluation to human performance. [published 7 September 2024] [CRD42024584166]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Clinical Prediction Models for Post-Stroke Depression: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis [published 16 January 2025] [CRD42025635227]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Predictors of Malignancy and Adverse Outcomes in Pediatric Patients with Thyroid Nodules: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis [published 14 May 2025] [CRD420251053103]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Diagnostic Accuracy of Deep Learning Algorithms in Detecting Odontogenic Cysts and Tumors Using Panoramic Images: A Systematic Review [published 2 June 2025] [CRD420251056622]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- The Role of Machine Learning in Enhancing Myocardial Infarction Detection: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis [published 16 January 2025] [CRD42025635148]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Risk Prediction Model for Anastomotic Leak After Rectal Cancer Surgery: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis [published 14 March 2025] [CRD420251011930]. The review was judged **not to be similar**

PROSPERO version history

- [Version 1.0, published 26 Jun 2025](#)

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